

On the Colour Reaction of Certain Nitro Compounds.

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m-Dinitrobenzene gives an unstable violet colour with laevulose in alkaline solution. This observation was made by Chavassieu and Morel (*Compt. rend.*, 1906, **143**, 966). Quite recently Truhaut (*J. Pharm. chim.*, 1933, **125**, 339) has observed that the same nitro compound gives a stable and characteristic violet colour with uric acid in alkaline medium. This observation of Truhaut has been criticised by Bose (*Current Science*, 1934, **2**, 427) who has proved that absolutely pure *m*-dinitrobenzene does not give any colour reaction of the above type whereas *o*-dinitrobenzene even in traces does so. The colour reactions observed by Truhaut and by Chavassieu and Morel are due to traces of *o*-dinitrobenzene present as impurity in *m*-dinitrobenzene. Bose has further demonstrated that *o*-dinitrobenzene gives the same characteristic violet colour with aldoses and ketoses (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1932, **87**, 110) as also with polyhydroxybenzenes having at least two hydroxy-groups in the *para*- or *ortho*-position to one another (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, *Sir P. C. Rây Volume*, 1933, p. 65).

Quite recently Péronnet and Truhaut (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1933, **53-54**, 1465) have further described a method for the determination of benzene vapour in air based on the conversion of benzene into *m*-dinitrobenzene by the action of a mixture of fuming nitric and concentrated sulphuric acids at a low temperature, and by measuring the intensity of colour developed by the '*m*-dinitrobenzene' in alcoholic and alkaline solution with the reducing sugar laevulose under certain experimental conditions. What happens in this case is that a certain amount of *o*-dinitrobenzene is formed as a bye-product during the nitration of benzene and this *ortho*-compound gives the colour reaction. The success of the method, therefore, would depend on two factors :

(i) The nitration must be carried out under definite experimental conditions, since variations of temperature, concentration of acids, etc., would result in a variation of the amount of *o*-dinitrobenzene formed.

(ii) A sufficient amount of impure *m*-dinitrobenzene (25-125 mg.) must be used for the colorimetry. A smaller amount would contain too little *ortho*-compound to give a stable colour.

In this connection it seemed desirable to study the behaviour of *ortho*-dinitro compounds in general towards alkaline reducing agents specially towards an alkaline solution of uric acid. The nitro compounds were taken in the form of 1-0.5% solution in absolute alcohol and 1-2 drops of this solution were added to 1 c.c. of a solution of uric acid (2.5 g. of acid dissolved in 100 c.c. of water containing 2.5 g. of potassium hydroxide) and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath. In some cases a colouration was observed at room temperature which either deepened or changed on being further heated. The following table shows the results obtained.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Colour	reaction
	At 25°.	At 100°.
1 :2-Dinitrobenzene	Violet	Deep violet
4-Chloro-1 :2-dinitrobenzene	„	Bluish violet
3 :4-Dichloro-1 :2-dinitrobenzene	...	Cherry-red
3 :5-Dichloro-1 :2-dinitrobenzene	Violet	Bluish violet
3 :6-Dichloro-1 :2-dinitrobenzene	...	Yellow
4 :5-Dichloro-1 :2-dinitrobenzene	Violet	Indigo-blue
3 :4 :5-Trichloro-1 :2-dinitrobenzene	Greenish yellow	Purplish brown
2 :3-Dinitrotoluene	...	Violet
3 :4-Dinitrotoluene	...	„
2 :3-Dinitroanisole	...	„
3 :4-Dinitroanisole	...	„
2 :3-Dinitroaniline	Yellow	Yellow
2 :3-Dinitroacetanilide	Pale green	Violet
3 :4-Dinitroaniline	...	„
3 :4-Dinitroacetanilide	...	Reddish violet
6-Chloro-2 :3-dinitroaniline	Yellow	Violet
6-Chloro-2 :3-dinitroacetanilide	Straw yellow	Yellow
2 :5-Dichloro-3 :4 dinitroacetanilide	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow
1 :2 :3-Trinitrobenzene	Violet brown	Violet-brown
4-Chloro-1 :2 :3-trinitrobenzene	Dirty violet	Dirty violet
5-Chloro-1 :2 :3-trinitrobenzene	„	„
1 :2 :4-Trinitrobenzene	Yellow brown	Yellow brown
6-Chloro-1 :2 :4-trinitrobenzene	Brown	Brown
1 :4-Dinitrobenzene	„	„
2 :3 :4 :6-Tetranitrophenol	Orange	Orange
3 :4-Dinitro- <i>o</i> -xylene	Cherry red	Cherry-red

From the foregoing results certain conclusions can be drawn thus:

(i) Aromatic *o*-dinitro compounds in general develop with suitable reducing substances in alkaline medium colour varying from cherry red to indigo-blue.

(ii) Chlorine atoms or NH_2 - groups in the proximity of the *ortho*-nitro groups hinder the development of any colour but yellow.

(iii) Compounds having nitro groups in the *para*-position to one another develop yellow to brown colour.

The development of colour in the above instances is to be attributed to the quinonoid salt of the type

and this has been definitely proved by Meisenheimer (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 4174) in the case of *o*-dinitrobenzene.

In conclusion, we wish to express our best thanks to Profs. A. F. Holleman and J. P. Wibaut for a gift of most of the compounds used in this investigation.

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